

Care and Protection of Children in Covid 19

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Abstract

A change in anything affects children first. COVID-19 has brought major crises which have impacted millions of population. It becomes more severe for the children who fall under the category of need of care and protection, significantly. Children who are institutionalised are being protected and facilitated with health, education and other basic needs during the global pandemic. On the other hand, those children who are left on roads, streets and hidden places become more traumatised. They face cumulative trauma. Normal was not enough for the children even after COVID-19. Children who face the worst circumstances in their childhood, they develop the victimhood thinking pattern and accordingly they look at themselves, hence they keep growing in this direction of life. COVID-19 has brought complex multiplicity and adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) of mental health problems in children such as anger, fear and hopelessness. UNICEF report shows behavioural symptoms among children grouped by age under 5 years, between 5-10 years and 10-19 years of children (UNICEF,). Hence, it is important to seize the learning for the future pandemic when dealing with the children.

Key words: Mental Health, COVID-19, Need of Care and Protection, Childhood experiences.

Introduction

A very famous and widely used line is the sky's the limit for the people who believe in dreams. But do children know what the sky is ? Dreams are far away, they don't even know about the sky. Such children are those who have been living under the worst circumstances of child labour and exploitation of any kind. As per the Juvenile justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2000 there are two categories of children identified. One of its kind is Child in Need of Care and Protection (CNCP) which includes the types of children like child labour, Prevention of Children from Sexual Offences (POCSO), missing children, trafficked children, single parent and many more. The other is Child in Conflict with Law (CNLP).

Child labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act, 1986 prohibits employment of children below the age of 14 years. The worst circumstances are found in the work pattern and the infrastructure primarily which can be seen to the most naive society as well.

Where do these children come from ? The employer takes the vulnerable children under the false promises made to the family saying that their children would get food, education and some amount of money for their living expenses. Another way that the children are taken from the village is trafficking. This is in the form of illegal and forced movement of humans from one state to another. Constantly living in such adverse conditions, children face all kinds of problems which are of different nature. The effect of exploitation is so much that children forget to live their dreams. And not only this, they forget their home address and home phone number and sometimes even the names of their parents if they are at the very early age of their childhood. As per the estimate 7 children go missing each hour in India. Because the subject matter is pervasive and draws global attention to supply chains that focus on ethical sourcing which is linked to children's fundamental rights, health and safety. The effect of child exploitation has a very deep impact on the overall growth and development of the children. There is outrightly said evidence which shows the development delay among child labourers. Children are forced to work for more than 15 hours a day under the 4 walls in a secret and hidden place. The employers keep a secret place where the children can be strictly hidden if the raid is being done by the administration so that no one can see if there is involvement of child labour at the worksite. From the process of getting children forcefully to work to the process of rescue, they face multiple kinds of abuse like emotional and physical (ILRF, 2011).

Children's one day routine is enough to explain many years of traumatic experiences they have gone through as their schedule starts while working on the field rather than going to the school, reading and playing with friends. They are always in such a hurry to work that they skip meals even two times in a day as decided by the employer. The children are not allowed to eat when they are hungry. They work with people irrelevant of their age. Most often the eldest in the group is the leader who plays an authoritative role against the kids. The major age differences in the group intensify the emotional and physical abuse amongst younger children. To be able to work for longer hours they are forcibly intoxicated with tobacco and drugs which makes their life dependent on substances from an early age. During the counselling sessions, children sometimes shy to talk because their tooth decay is visible due to long time tobacco in-take at the worksite. They are ill-treated by the employer. Sometimes they become the object of being beaten and abused. In some cases it is found that such traumatic experiences at a young age adversely lead to forgotten memories regarding family and home address. They become away from their culture, social activities and their very own peer group.

Counselling Practice: A ground view

In the context of providing counselling services to children, there are certain important factors to be considered. The note on traumatic experiences of children is important in any counselling programme. It can be since from stepping for the first time outside the home till rescue process, it may be the most horrific situation a child encounters in their life. Children are vulnerable to different situations. Majorly children are victims of child labour, trafficking, street child, missing child, neglected child, sexually, physically and emotionally abused child etc. The box given below, providing stage wise intervention plan to consider during counselling.

1st Stage What the child sees	2nd Stage What the mind understand	3rd Stage What actually he/she suffers
Lack of trust by the child	Asked to trust on the strangers (employer, bystander, crowd, trafficker, abuser)	Damage of SELF, Physical and emotional abuse, mistrusted
False promise made by the abuser	False assurance of food and education	Faded childhood (food, play, education and love) and faded memories (family, address, phone number)
Regain of childhood: false dream shown by the abuser to the vulnerable family	Intend to get to use the mobile phone and money	Loss to dignified life, Family neglect and societal neglect, Children get missing from home
Firm belief in the good of the outer world: as soon as the family is convinced by the abuser, the child is also asked to get convinced.	Misconception to help family members financially	Deterioration of physical and mental health

Children may be at risk in circumstances: (i) where they lack opportunity and encouragement to develop a coherent sense of their identity(ies) within which they have self-respect; (ii) where they are forcibly separated from their family and community (as in trafficking); (iii) where they are surrounded by conflict, violence and social instability or where they (and their community) are subject to persecution; and (iv) where they are faced with confusing or competing expectations (e.g. incompatible and unreasonable demands for economic activity as well as school achievement). At worst their identity may be challenged where they feel degraded and stigmatised by their situation and by the ways they are treated (e.g. as in bonded labour or in sex work).

Modalities used during counselling sessions:

- **The House-Tree-Person** has been very helpful in collecting and connecting cues of a child's journey to life. The child feels connected with the activity and watches it standing in the outside world. Children are asked

to make a tree and name the most extended branch as the most important person of his own life. Following the series in the descending order, the child mentions the name or the position of known people in his life.

The most important part of this activity is children feel free to express their thoughts and feelings as they are not the prime character of that Tree. This paper activity is applicable on children across all ages. Once a child draws a picture the counsellor gathers the view of the world from the child's lens through images rather than words. Children have a hard time expressing their feelings with words and drawings can really help get a sense of what they see, think and feel.

It is found that when a missing child feels reluctant to share about the family cues, such activity is helpful to enable children to develop insight. This technique can offer detailed insight into the child's mind that he or she may not have words to describe to begin with (Buschel & Madsen, 2008).

- **Mapping (visual representation)** to develop and enhance interpersonal communication and mitigate anxiety level. A group of children participated in this activity. One child narrated the fictional story while the other was making pictures with characters on the ground to make the other children understand in an easy way based on the story. Their method has attracted other children to listen and add new stories to it. The session has identified the children's interest areas in story formation as well as projection. This helps children to choose any resources in order to represent ideas which are central to the theme. Children tend to use the best of symbols to represent stories in more summarised and creative ways. This will enable them with divergent thinking and problem-solving approaches in everyday life.
- **Mirror technique:** Mirror technique will effectively help the client to develop emotional resilience and self-awareness. For example the child would attempt to explore himself/herself through this technique. For instance child says that " Hello, my name is A and I belong to Hyderabad. Hello, my name is A and I belong to Delhi", having more sentence manipulations about self-introduction to different people at a time from the same client shows the excitement and struggle to present himself. Drawing the very specific interest of the client through observation in self-grooming, mirror as a facilitator tool enhances combing hair, after washing, cleaning of face and keeping a check of how one is looking out of fear/excitement. This technique is instrumental to see the present in the mirror and find out what has led the client to disconnect himself from the world. The activity followed with a series of counselling sessions. At the initial stage of the affected mirror , there is a slight discomfort. Gradually after 4-5 activity sessions the client experiences reflections of feelings and all kinds of emotional expressions during the conversation to self. This advances multiple factors like speech, eye movement, twitching of face and blinking of eyes, hand movement and gestures. Consequently, it helps the client and the counsellor together where the struggle lies and therefore paraphrase the words. The concept of self becomes more clearer with mirror reflection. This technique is one way to address the past trauma that the client has gone through where the SELF is entirely damaged by the environmental stimuli.
- **Ecotherapy: Collection of natural resources to counselling sessions:** Ecotherapy refers to both the healing and the growth that is nurtured by healthy interaction with the earth (Clinebell).

The technique of the session is very close to role-play where few missing and nonmissing children participated. The missing children were asked to use the best way to take the help of existing resources in order to fulfil what is required when the guest is coming to their house. Each session has a number of guests (the children) including the counsellor and one different host (The client:missing child). In India, children grow up while playing in the soil. They sense the armour by touch and smell. The soil activity allows them to interact with the environment and come close to nature. The number of sessions conducted was equal to the number of missing children because each session was hosted by each child. They made food from the plant's leaves, served the food on a big leaf, and welcomed guests with water and some sweets like biscuits. Each child's approach was different. They were necessarily supposed to take the help of family members present in the imagined house. The clues of the home of missing children the Counselor can get is amazingly valuable to acknowledge and document well. Each clue is helpful in connecting the dots of a child's life. When the child is consciously sitting in the session, he/she is not able to tell anything about the family because they adopt a pattern of behaviour in their habit to not to say NO whenever asked about the time spent in the family.

- **Video Modelling (VM):** Learning by observing others is the most effective component that the children start learning from a very young age. We do things as we see others in the family doing. Since childhood, we have had the sweet enchantment of narration by our grandparents, who told us the stories of the Queen

Special Issue on 'Covid-19 Pandemic and Well Being : Perspectives on Social Aspects' and the King. You would start with imagination, and make an effort in forming the whole story. Likewise our life, and having a holistic view of things, is dependent on each part of our imagination.

Therefore, imagination is a process of evolving through the stages of life. It is more or less related to visualising things that might be beyond one's physical limitations. Somewhere, imagination helps us to apply our knowledge, to know about ourselves, to look more closely at our own thoughts and perceptions. In this way video modelling technique plays a very efficient role when dealing with the counselling sessions of children.

There are numerous strategies available to promote student engagement, including the creation of learning that is active and collaborative, challenging and enriching, and that meets children's expectations (Zepke & Leach, 2010)

Children view videos with their own lens of understanding and start forming an image. It is important to use the transformative pedagogy which is most likely to demonstrate a particular kind of knowledge. Use of elements to learn in the form of gadgets-approach always amazes children which increases their interest in the subject matter.

A group of children were shown a silent short black-and-white video casting solely on sound and music without the use of verbatim. All densely packed in 12 minutes. Two boys both 6-7 years old, duelling with each other in the middle of a lonely and breezy summer afternoon. The video shows the deep emotional reactions of two children belonging from two different class societies and their different ways of handling loneliness. Children were asked to draw instruments that were strongly used to narrate the story in the video clip. They drew pictures of flutes and pistols. Then, the same was used as the blindfolded chit to gamify the session. Afterwards, two children acted on the story and then was explained by one of the children to discourage teasing behaviour with each other (Vicarious learning with the support of video counselling). Children noticed videos based on their life experiences. Post view discussion by each child was entirely different. For some children it challenges their worldview so they make an effort to fit the view in their own understanding of what they have experienced so far out of fear, anger, mistrust, and exploitation acted against by the employer or the trafficker.

It has also been documented that the use of the VM method has had a positive impact on the counselling students (Larson et al., 1999; Munson et al., 1986). After the post viewing discussion, many challenges came up in the light to address during the counselling sessions like interpersonal attachment, conflict with one another, one's own perception and the trauma faced while being neglected from the family and the society.

Children at Rehabilitation Centre during Covid-19 and the Possible Applications

There have been two sides to work with the children. One is to develop a safety net for children against exploitation of any form and the other is to develop a safety net against pandemic Covid-19 crises. Unexpected forced transition for the institutionalised children led to complexities in understanding that there will be movement restriction and nobody is allowed to move outside of the centre. Such things were not normal for anyone. Children experienced physical isolation from friends, school teachers and family members. This led to the problem of loneliness, boredom, fatigue, hopelessness and fear of uncertainty. Anxiety and distress has no match when it comes to the mental health covid-19 implications on children. Interventional strategies based on the following factors:

- Awareness on prevention from Covid-19
- Balanced diet nutrition
- Indoor and outdoor activities
- Addressing physical and mental health care
- Ensuring children's contact with their family members and friends
- Normalisation

Restoration and Prevention

The author experienced while working with children , that there are many creative ways to engage children. Some of the activities are mentioned here.

- **Building resilience:** Teaching resilience to the children and practising it especially during Covid-19 has made them to patiently care for each other. To inculcate the care and affection among fellows, children were taken to the ground where plants and trees are nurtured.

They were encouraged to seed the new plants and water the old ones. This activity was followed in all the divided groups of children. They were asked to check on old and new ones everyday in the morning and the evening. The thematic area was asked by the children to decide on why we are doing this especially during the crises as we used

to follow the same plantation activity everyday. So the younger children responded that as soon as the trees grow old and new plants begin to blossom, that will decide how long we are going to stand together in this crisis. The rhythm in the everyday activity was added by the birds chirping which children used to enjoy a lot by different birds. Such eco-therapy techniques help children to remain close to nature and live the cherished moment.

- **Cultural evening:** The super fun moment for the children is when they do dance, music and theatre whereas few others enjoy just by watching too. This helps in release of stress and they feel energetic when their favourite music-beat echoes in the surrounding.
- **In campus awareness program:** Virtual outsourced awareness program for the children was regularly being conducted. They made art and craft using papers in the form of awareness flyers. The process of making awareness kits for themselves brings a sense of pride among the children regarding their collective contribution to the society.
- **Periodic telephonic interaction with friends and families :** It was kept to ensure that the children are in contact with their family members and friends through telephones beyond physical limitations. The most curious part is when these children shared the different mindsets of their native towns about corona and stigma. Because of the running awareness program, children used to educate their families on the crisis over the phone call.
- **Language precision techniques :** With increased impatience over lockdown and movement, children easily indulged into fighting and quarrelsome behaviour with one another which disturbs their interpersonal relationship.

In order to reduce the friendship crisis, the focus was given on the use of language. While using positive distortions, use of language helped to maintain the relationship among children. Children were taught different ways of expressing intentional words to their fellows.

Conclusion

The first severe pandemic of the 21st century has addressed the gap in standards of prevention of the virus and mental health measurable. With physical-social isolation children also get affected with psychological isolation. To meet the prevention set standards from the virus, certain actions required to slow down the spread such as ventilation, masks, and vaccines. Instilling hope in the child survivors is the present challenge. It becomes more significant when the children's quality life is severely interfered with and makes a long lasting adverse impact in the areas of health, education and outdoor play during Covid-19. Translating the right skill set for the children is important to meet their emotional needs in today's changing environment. Kindness, on the road of counselling, is a very important key to care for self and others. Therefore, cultivating the act of kindness and empathy brings transformation in the counselling practice.

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